

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUSTAPHA****FIRST NAME: GREMA****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 4%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D.

1. In developing a qualitative dissertation, specific components of the dissertation are required to strengthen the overall quality of the dissertation by stimulating the early involvement of the supervisory committee. What could that component be?

- Dissertation Concept Paper.¹**
- Research Question and Hypothesis of the Dissertation
- The Dissertation Manuscript
- Identifying and Developing the Research Topic.

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

2. The five core guiding principles Reilly and Kiyimba (2015) put forward for designing and evaluating the quality of qualitative work include:
- Cursory review, Ethicality, Scholarly, Positivism and Postmodernism.
 - Flexibility, Transferability, Ethicality, Social Interpretivism, and Reflectivity.
 - Integrity, Ethicality, Positivism, Reflectivity, and Criticality.
 - Transparency, Flexibility, Transferability, Ethicality, and Integrity.**²
3. In academic writing, what punctuation can be used to identify words and phrases that are not necessarily quotes but to draw attention to lexical items?
- Apostrophe.
 - Comma.
 - Quotation Mark.**³
 - Forward Slash.
4. The dissertation manuscript entails a concise presentation of the literature review, the research questions, the research methods, the findings, the discussion of findings, and the research implications. Based on your understanding, what is the primary rationale for preparing the dissertation manuscript?
- Complete the critical analysis of the literature and formulate research questions.
 - To promote objectivity as a vital component of the dissertation.

² Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019), 93–94.

³ European Union, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eight Edition (European Commission's Directorate-General for Translation, 2016), 14.

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Publication in a peer-reviewed journal, monograph, book, or book chapter.⁴

5. What are the six primary factors or good practices contributing to successful Dissertation Research?

Collaboration, Early start-up, Frequent meetings with Major Supervisors, Good Planning, Adopting an effective Writing Process, and good planning.

Early engagement with the review committee, collaboration with other researchers, good communication, Serendipity, Visualizing, and good planning.

Good communication, Good Planning, Using an effective Process for Writing, Attention to Detail, Openness to Serendipity, and Visualizing Success.⁵

Using an effective Process for Writing, Collaboration, Frequent Meetings with Major Supervisors, Good Planning, and Visualizing Success.

6. In academic writing, one must credit sources consulted, or ideas of other authors derived from sources consulted through proper citation. This helps to mitigate plagiarism. However, there are instances where some ideas must be limited. Kindly select the correct instance from the options below.

When the information or idea used is adequately paraphrased.

When the information or idea used is not from a scholarly source.

When the purpose of the writing is not to fulfill any academic endeavor.

⁴ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 5.

⁵ Ibid., 13–15.

When the information or idea is used is a common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas.⁶

7. It is essential to ensure that foreign words and phrases used in English texts during writing are utilized and not singled out through a quotation mark. Foreign words used should also maintain their appropriate accents. However, italics are not required for certain characters and words. Please select the proper option where the use of italics is not needed.

Proper names, individual titles, and non-English words.

Proper names, names of persons, institutions, places, etc.⁷

Proper names only.

Institutions only.

8. In academic writing, it is essential to maintain coherence and use plain English that readers can easily understand. However, certain Latin abbreviations are appropriate in certain sections of the body of work. From the options listed below, please select the relevant section where the Latin abbreviation can be used.

Footnotes, appendices, and bibliographies.

Table of contents, footnotes, and bibliographies.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 37.

⁷ European Union, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 48.

Footnotes, Bibliographies, and Informal writings.⁸

In-text citations, appendices, and table of contents.

9. In academic writing, knowledge of institutionally adopted formats or styles like dissertation outlines, acceptable style guides, referencing, etc., can assist students in preparing a very qualitative dissertation. Recognizing the importance of these, what is the first page to be numbered?

Abstract.⁹

Introduction.

Acknowledgment.

Table of Contents.

10. If ideas or concepts are critical and add significant insight to one's research argument, they should be cited appropriately to give credit and avoid plagiarism. Ideas and concepts derived from unpublished interviews and or personal communications should only be cited in the following:

Bibliography.

Both bibliography and footnote.

There are no specific sections of the dissertation.

Footnote.¹⁰

⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 59.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 68.

¹⁰ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 200–201.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D., and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*. Fourth Edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.